

Short Note on P vs NP

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Abstract

Under the assumption of certain hypothesis, we show that $P \neq NP$. In this way, we provide another possible tool to prove the P versus NP problem.

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1 Result

A principal NP -complete problem is SAT [2]. An instance of SAT is a Boolean formula ϕ which is composed of:

1. Boolean variables: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
2. Boolean connectives: Any Boolean function with one or two inputs and one output, such as \wedge (AND), \vee (OR), \neg (NOT), \Rightarrow (implication), \Leftrightarrow (if and only if);
3. and parentheses.

A truth assignment for a Boolean formula ϕ is a set of values for the variables in ϕ . A satisfying truth assignment is a truth assignment that causes ϕ to be evaluated as true. A Boolean formula with a satisfying truth assignment is satisfiable. The problem SAT asks whether a given Boolean formula is satisfiable [2]. We define a CNF Boolean formula using the following terms:

A literal in a Boolean formula is an occurrence of a variable or its negation [1]. A Boolean formula is in conjunctive normal form, or CNF , if it is expressed as an AND of clauses, each of which is the OR of one or more literals [1]. A Boolean formula is in 3-conjunctive normal form or $3CNF$, if each clause has exactly three distinct literals [1]. For example, the Boolean formula:

$$(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2) \wedge (x_3 \vee x_2 \vee x_4) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$$

is in $3CNF$. The first of its three clauses is $(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2)$, which contains the three literals x_1 , $\neg x_1$, and $\neg x_2$. We state the following Hypothesis on Boolean formulas in $3CNF$:

► **Hypothesis 1.** *There is a general fixed constant c for all set of variables $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and a set of truth assignments T_X assigned to X such that there exists a satisfiable Boolean formula ϕ in $3CNF$ using a set of variables Y with at most n^c variables and $X \subseteq Y$. For each satisfying truth assignment T in ϕ , we have there is at least a truth assignment $T' \in T_X$ such that $T' \subseteq T$, which means T' is mapped into the variables in X . For every truth assignment $T' \in T_X$, there exists at least a satisfying truth assignment T in ϕ such that $T' \subseteq T$. Moreover, there is no a satisfying truth assignment T in ϕ such that a truth assignment T' is mapped into the variables in X , $T' \subseteq T$ and $T' \notin T_X$.*

A graph $G = (V, E)$ has V as the set of vertices and E as the set of edges, each edge being a pair of vertices [1]. We say $(u, v) \in E$ is an edge in a graph $G = (V, E)$ where u and v are vertices: We say that u and v are adjacent. For a graph $G = (V, E)$, a simple path in G is a sequence of distinct vertices $\langle v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k \rangle$ such that $(v_{i-1}, v_i) \in E$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ [1]. A

Hamilton path is a simple path of a graph which contains all the vertices of the graph [1]. Interestingly, a linear order P on the nodes of G describes the existence of a Hamilton path, that is, a binary relationship isomorphic to $<$ on the nodes of G (without loss of generality, these nodes are $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$) such that consecutive nodes are connected in G [3]. The properties of P require several things. We say that a tuple (x, y) is appropriated for the binary relation P when (x, y) belongs to P . First, all distinct nodes of G are comparable by P [3]:

$$\forall x \forall y ((P(x, y) \vee P(y, x)) \vee x = y).$$

Next, P must be transitive but not reflexive [3]:

$$\forall x \forall y \forall z ((\neg P(x, x)) \wedge ((P(x, y) \wedge P(y, z)) \Rightarrow P(x, z))).$$

Finally, any two consecutive nodes in P must be adjacent in G [3]:

$$\forall x \forall y ((P(x, y) \wedge \forall z (\neg P(x, z) \vee \neg P(z, y))) \Rightarrow G(x, y))$$

where $G(x, y)$ means that (x, y) is an edge on G . The existence of such linear order P with these properties guarantee the existence of a Hamilton path on G [3].

In computational complexity theory, *SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH* is a well-known problem in *NEXP-complete* [3]. A succinct representation of a graph with n nodes, where $n = 2^b$ is a power of two, is a Boolean circuit C with $2 \times b$ input gates [3]. The graph represented by C , denoted G_C , is defined as follows: The nodes of G_C are $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$ and (i, j) is an edge of G_C if and only if C accepts the binary representations of the b -bits integers i, j as input [3].

► **Definition 2. SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH**

INSTANCE: A succinct representation C of a graph G_C with n nodes.

QUESTION: Does G_C have a Hamilton path?

REMARKS: We know that *SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH* \in *NEXP-complete* [3].

Given a succinct representation C of a graph G_C with n nodes, where $n = 2^b$ is a power of two, if the Hypothesis 1 is true and $C \in$ *SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH*, then there exists a Boolean formula Q in *3CNF* bounded by less than $(3 \times b)^c$ variables and $(3 \times b)^{4 \times c}$ clauses. $Q(x, y)$ means the remaining formula after evaluating Q in the first $2 \times b$ variables that correspond to the bits of the b -bits integers x, y . In addition, Q could represent a linear order P such that $P(x, y)$ holds if and only if the Boolean formula $Q(x, y)$ is satisfiable. Similarly, we say that $C(x, y)$ accepts when the Boolean circuit C has been evaluated in the binary representations of the b -bits integers x, y and the output is 1 (or simply true). Moreover, this linear order P that represents Q could comply the properties mentioned above when G_C has a Hamilton path and thus, we can confirm that $C \in$ *SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH*.

We can apply the Hypothesis 1 and obtain the formula Q , because the linear order P is a binary relation between integers represented by a set of variables $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{2 \times b}\}$ and a set of truth assignments T_X assigned to X , where T_X contains the truth assignments for the $2 \times b$ variables that correspond to the bits of the b -bits integers x, y when (x, y) belongs to P . Since the set X has a cardinality of $2 \times b$, the set of variables in Q has at most $(2 \times b)^c$ elements (this is bounded by the amount of $(3 \times b)^c$). Since every clause of a formula in *3CNF* has exactly 3 literals, then we would obtain at most a combination of $2 \times (2 \times b)^c$ literals within sets of three elements (this is bounded by the amount of $(3 \times b)^{4 \times c}$). Note that, the set X corresponds to the first $2 \times b$ variables in Q and so, every appropriated

tuple (x, y) in the binary relation P would be a truth assignment to the variables in X that will be contained into a satisfying truth assignment of Q . Indeed, $Q(x, y)$ will be a satisfiable formula if and only if the pair (x, y) belongs to P , because of the Hypothesis 1 which guarantee the existence of such Boolean formula Q and its constraints.

Basically, we could represent an appropriated tuple (x, y) of the linear order P if and only if $Q(x, y)$ is satisfiable. In this way, we could represent the first property of P :

$$\forall x \forall y ((P(x, y) \vee P(y, x)) \vee x = y)$$

as the computational problem of solving the Boolean formula with quantified variables,

$$\forall x \forall y ((Q(x, y) \vee Q(y, x)) \vee \psi(x, y))$$

where the Boolean formula ψ is satisfied when $x = y$. We can see that, the other variables in Q , which are not in the set X , remain as free variables inside of this kind of Boolean formula. In addition, we could represent the other properties:

$$\forall x \forall y \forall z ((\neg P(x, x)) \wedge ((P(x, y) \wedge P(y, z)) \Rightarrow P(x, z))).$$

and

$$\forall x \forall y ((P(x, y) \wedge \forall z (\neg P(x, z) \vee \neg P(z, y))) \Rightarrow G(x, y))$$

as the computational problems of solving the Boolean formulas with quantified variables,

$$\forall x \forall y \forall z ((\neg Q(x, x)) \wedge ((Q(x, y) \wedge Q(y, z)) \Rightarrow Q(x, z))).$$

and

$$\forall x \forall y ((Q(x, y) \wedge \forall z (\neg Q(x, z) \vee \neg Q(z, y))) \Rightarrow F(x, y))$$

where F is the Boolean function that represents the circuit C ($F(x, y)$ is satisfied if and only if $C(x, y)$ accepts). We know the bit-length of the formulas $Q(x, y)$, $\psi(x, y)$ and $F(x, y)$ are polynomially bounded by the bit-length of the circuit C according to the Hypothesis 1 since all problems in P have polynomial circuits such as checking whether two sequences of bits are equals or whether a Boolean circuit accepts after being evaluated all its input gates [3].

Note also that, solving those Boolean formulas with quantified variables signifies the necessity of computing instances of problems that can be solved in polynomial time when $P = NP$ [3]. Under the assumption that $P = NP$, we would have a succinct certificate for the instance $C \in \text{SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH}$ that could be the formula Q , where we should be able to check the existence of the Hamilton path using Q by a deterministic Turing machine in polynomial time. However, this is exactly the definition of NP . If there is any single problem in $NEXP$ -complete that it is also in NP , then $NP = NEXP$. However, $NP \neq NEXP$ is a previous known result [3]. If we assume that $P = NP$ and the Hypothesis 1 is true, then this implies that $\text{SUCCINCT HAMILTON PATH}$ should be in NP which is trivial contradiction. Consequently, we obtain that necessarily $P \neq NP$ under the assumption that the Hypothesis 1 is true.

References

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